

NORMAL TRAFFIC MODES OF VEHICLES ON CITY STREETS AND ROADS

Mutalibov Ibroxim Qosimjon o'g'li

intern-teacher

(Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute)

Annotation: Regulation of traffic safety on the streets and roads of the city is primarily aimed at ensuring the life, health and property of citizens, as well as their rights and legal interests, as well as environmental protection. A crosswalk is a place where traffic is restricted and pedestrians can move safely.

Key words: Accidents, bad weather, sidewalk, road safety, traffic accidents, traffic rules, road signs, roadside, drainage system.

INTRODUCTION

Extensive organizational and practical work has been carried out in recent years in the field of improving the system of ensuring the safety of road traffic in our country. At the same time, despite the measures taken, the number of road traffic accidents leading to death is still is also prominent and shows the need for a fundamental reform of the system of ensuring safety in automobiles. In particular, it is required to fully coordinate the infrastructure of the railway with the modern requirements of ensuring traffic safety, to establish an effective system aimed at the early prevention of violations in this area, as well as to widely implement digital technologies that exclude the human factor. In accordance with the strategy for the development of the public safety system in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021-2025.

Violations of the normal movement of vehicles on city streets and roads may result in the death of people, physical injuries, as well as damage to vehicles and their loads, damage to artificial structures on the road, or other types of material damage. Accidents causing traffic accidents are called road traffic accidents.

When a traffic accident occurs, it is observed that one or more of the elements of "A-H-Y-P-M" (car-driver-road-pedestrian-environment) that are part of the general system together cause a violation of the normal movement mode.[1]

Three phases can be conventionally distinguished in each traffic accident: initial, culminating and final. They are interrelated, and one can be a continuation of the other.

The initial phase of a traffic accident is defined as the traffic conditions of cars and pedestrians on the verge of a dangerous situation. A dangerous situation is understood as a traffic condition in which the participants of the traffic have enough opportunities to prevent a traffic accident, if this opportunity is not used quickly or the measures taken are not effective enough, then the approach of cars and pedestrians is catastrophic (accident) creates a situation. The culminating phase of a traffic accident is characterized by the occurrence of serious consequences (vehicle breakdown, injuries or death of pedestrians and drivers). This phase can last a few minutes, and in bad weather conditions up to several minutes. In this case, several vehicles are usually involved, and it is often called a "chain" traffic accident.[2] The final phase of a traffic accident is the end of the traffic stop after the culminating phase. Sometimes the final phase continues even if the vehicle stops moving. For example, cases of fire in an overturned car.

According to the current regulatory documents, the traffic accident consists of the following 9 types:[3]

1. Collision. This includes head-on, head-on or side-to-side collisions, as well as road and rail collisions. This type of traffic accident also includes a collision with a vehicle that has stopped suddenly.

2. Overturning (overturning). A moving vehicle overturns after losing its stability. This type of traffic accident does not include collisions, overturning of vehicles as a result of hitting parked vehicles or barriers. A rollover traffic accident usually involves one vehicle.

3. Hitting a stationary vehicle. Collision of a moving vehicle with a stationary (V=0) vehicle. This type of traffic accident does not include a sudden (sudden) stop of a vehicle.

4. Crashing into obstacles. Crashing of vehicles into immovable obstacles (bridge support, pillar and mast support, road barriers, trees, etc.).

5. Hitting pedestrians. This includes vehicles striking pedestrians or pedestrians striking vehicles, as well as injuries to pedestrians from transported cargo (timber, pipes, slabs, etc.).

6. Hitting a cyclist. A vehicle hits (hits) a cyclist or a cyclist hits a vehicle.

7. Hitting the cart. A moving vehicle hits a moving cart, and this type also includes a vehicle hitting a wild or domestic animal.

8. Passenger's fall.

9. Other (remaining) traffic accident. This type of traffic accident includes a tram derailing and hitting a vehicle or pedestrians, accidents caused by cargo falling from trucks, injuries caused by stones or other solid objects coming out from under the wheel of a car, etc. enters.

High speed increases the driver's exposure to a potential collision and reduces braking distance, while reducing the time available to avoid a collision. As a result, the probability of injuries and the severity of injuries in car accidents increases by three times, and the probability of becoming victims increases by two times. When a vehicle hits a pedestrian at an average speed of 30 km/h, the pedestrian has a 10% chance of death, at a speed of 40 km/h - 25%, and at a speed of 50 km/h - with a probability of 55%. The higher the speed of the vehicle, the shorter the time it takes for the driver to stop and avoid a collision, i.e. hitting a pedestrian (see Figure 1).

Driver's emergency

Figure 1. A graph of the relationship between speed and braking distance.

We can also see from the conducted research that high speed increases the risk of death of pedestrians. We can see this in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. In an accident involving a pedestrian, a graph of the probability of a pedestrian being killed as a function of the speed of a motor vehicle.

From the graph above, we can see that the higher the speed, the higher the probability of pedestrian death. And the probability of death increases when the speed exceeds 50 km/h. For this reason, the speed limit on city streets of developed countries is 30 km/h, and on city roads is 50 km/h. If we pay attention to the mutual group of pedestrians, for certain groups of pedestrians, the speed of 30 km/h remains high probability of death.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the factors affecting the road traffic accident and their participants, the reasons for its occurrence, and the research and analysis of car

accidents in the world and their participants were widely covered. It was found that the main participants of traffic accidents are the driver-road-environment-pedestrian-cars.

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